

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A WOUND-HEALING DRUG BASED ON MICRONIZED KAOLINITE AND ESSENTIAL OILS OF KAZAKHSTAN PLANTS

Kozhanova K.K.
Kadyrbayeva G.M.
Bekezhanova T.S.
Karabayeva A.A.,
Zhaparkulova K.A.
Ziyat A.I.

Asfendiyarov Kazakh National Medical University, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan

e-mail: kozhanova.k@kaznmu.kz, tel.: +7-701-738-86-25

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Relevance: The problem of infected wounds remains one of the key challenges in clinical practice. The growing prevalence of multidrug-resistant microbial strains and the increasing demand for domestic medicines that combine antimicrobial activity, hemostatic effect, and the ability to stimulate tissue repair processes are evident. Natural geomaterials (including kaolin/kaolinite) have already demonstrated clinical efficacy as safe hemostatics and as matrices for the delivery of active substances, while essential oils (EOs) of Kazakhstan's plants exhibit pronounced antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activities.

Aim of the study. To conduct a critical review of the scientific literature on the use of micronized kaolinite in combination with essential oils, to evaluate pharmacological, technological, and toxicological aspects, and to develop recommendations for creating a wound-healing drug on their basis.

Material (literature review). The review covered: experimental data on kaolinite as a hemostatic and carrier agent; studies on polymer-clay dressings with antimicrobial properties; data on the composition and bioactivity of EOs from Kazakhstan plants; publications on the safety of EO components; and reviews on release kinetics and stability of EOs in matrices.

Results. Analysis of the literature showed that kaolinite provides a rapid hemostatic effect and can serve as a matrix for creating porous dressings with proven clinical efficacy. Essential oils containing thymol, carvacrol, and other phenolic compounds demonstrate antibacterial, antifungal, and regenerative properties, while their incorporation into polymer matrices enhances antimicrobial effects and accelerates epithelialization. The feasibility of "clay + essential oil" compositions has been demonstrated, ensuring controlled release and improved stability of bioactive components. A limitation is the presence of potentially toxic compounds in EOs, necessitating dosage optimization, selection of safe essential oils, and mandatory preclinical toxicological evaluation.

Conclusion. The combination of micronized kaolinite and essential oils of Kazakhstan plants represents a promising platform for the development of a local wound-healing drug. Recommendations for further research include: selection of prospective essential oil-bearing plants with proven pharmacological activity; extraction and study of essential oils; choice of dosage form (gels/sponges/dressings) with evaluation of adsorption and release kinetics; formulation development; stepwise biological assessment in vitro (MIC, cytotoxicity, collagenogenesis), followed by controlled in vivo wound-healing models and systemic toxicology; compliance with regulatory requirements for preclinical safety. If these conditions are met, the project has high translational potential, particularly when utilizing locally available plant raw materials. This study was carried out within the framework of the intramural grant of Asfendiyarov KazNMU «Development of technology

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and standardization of pharmaceutical products based on kaolinite clays and essential oils of medicinal plants».